

COMPARISON OF CDMA SPATIO-TEMPORAL RECEIVERS STRUCTURES FOR MULTI-RATE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Code division multiple access (CDMA) is the multiple access scheme retained for the third generation wireless communication systems, that must support high data rate transmissions, and operate over jammed Rayleigh fading channels. In the current work, we propose and analyze multi-antenna spatio-temporal adaptive receiving structures of detection at the base station, able to cope with degradations due to multiple access interferences. Their ability to reject part of the jammers, and their resistance to near-far effects is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Third generation wireless systems, such as the Universal Mobile Transmission System (UMTS), are required to accommodate a large variety of services, including in particular high data rate transmissions. Since higher data rate means higher transmit power, the receiver must face near-far problems. This paper investigates the performances of different receivers at the base station for multi-rate code division multiple access (CDMA) applications, in the presence of jammed frequency-selective fading channels. The conventional 2D-RAKE demodulator consists of a set of matched filters, and assumes that the noise is white and Gaussian. In realistic situations, this receiver suffers from multiple access interferences due to the cross-correlation between the users' codes, and near-far effects due to imperfect power control in the uplink. We propose a practical implementation of multisensor structures based on jammers rejection, combined with inter-symbol interference equalization. The Maximum Likelihood Sequence Estimator (MLSE), which is optimum for Gaussian interferers, is trained by a sequence of pilot symbols using two estimating techniques that have been previously settled in a GSM context [1]-[2]. The survey in perfect power control has been derived in [3] by the authors. Here we focus on the near-far effects that often occur in CDMA uplink communications, and in addition we examine the computational costs of each implementation. Simulations

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reveal that considerable improvements can be achieved by receivers that take account of the spatial and temporal color of the interferences for multi-rate applications. The paper is organized as follows: the MLSE structure and filters estimation are developed in section 2. Convenient low cost performance evaluation criteria are provided in section 3. Numerical results are given in section 4. Conclusions are summarized in section 5.

In the sequel, the superscripts T and $*$ stand respectively for transpose and transpose complex conjugate. The tilde notation $\tilde{x}(f)$ stands for the Fourier transform of the signal $x(t)$ sampled at rate f_e .

2 MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD SEQUENCE ESTIMATOR (MLSE)

CDMA single-user detection over a jammed frequency-selective fading channel is considered. The constant modulus symbols transmitted by the mobile of interest are denoted $(s_0, \dots, s_{N-1})$. Each symbol s_n is multiplied by a randomly generated scrambling code sequence $(c_n(0), \dots, c_n(\lambda - 1))$, where λ is the spreading factor. $\mathbf{x}(t) = [x_1(t) \ \dots \ x_P(t)]^T$ denotes the received signal at the P sensors antenna array, sampled at rate $f_e = 1/T_e$ multiple of the chip frequency $f_c = 1/T_c$. $\mathbf{g}(t) = [g_1(t) \ \dots \ g_P(t)]^T$ is the L -length composite channel for each sensor, defined by the convolution of the modulation shaping pulse with the channel impulse response, sampled at rate f_e . All the other users are considered as jammers, they are stationary complex circular Gaussian with power spectral density denoted $\tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{bb}(f)$.

The survey investigated in [4] for GSM systems leads to the receiver structure that maximizes the symbol sequence likelihood function (MLSE). This receiver utilizes spatio-temporal filter $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{MLSE}(f)$ and temporal filter $\tilde{i}_{MLSE}(f)$ defined by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{MLSE}(f) = \tilde{\mathbf{g}}^*(f) \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{bb}^{-1}(f) \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{MLSE}(f) = \frac{T_e}{T_c} \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{T_c}{T_e} - 1} \tilde{j}_{MLSE}(f + kf_c), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\tilde{j}_{MLSE}(f) = \tilde{\mathbf{g}}^*(f) \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{bb}^{-1}(f) \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(f). \quad (3)$$

The optimum demodulator is implemented with a Viterbi algorithm that maximizes the following criterion

$$J_{MLSE}(s_0, \dots, s_{N-1}) = \Re e \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} s_n^* y(n) \right) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} s_m^* \gamma(m, n) s_n. \quad (4)$$

In a CDMA context, signals $y(n)$ and $\gamma(m, n)$ depend on the scrambling code. They are defined by

$$y(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lambda-1} c_n^*(k) (\mathbf{w}_{MLSE}(t) * \mathbf{x}(t))_{t=(n\lambda+k)T_c}, \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma(m, n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lambda-1} \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} c_m^*(k) i_{MLSE}((\lambda(m-n) + k - l)T_c) c_n(l).$$

A sequence of pilot symbols is used to realize the practical estimation of the filters $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{MLSE}(f)$ and $\tilde{i}_{MLSE}(f)$. Two methods are proposed for these estimations. **The first method** has been introduced in [2] for GSM applications: the noise is modeled as a Gaussian vector valued auto-regressive (AR) process of order K

$$\mathbf{n}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{n}(t - kT_e) + \mathbf{e}(t), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{e}(t)$ is temporally white and spatially colored with covariance

$$E\{\mathbf{e}^*(nT_e)\mathbf{e}(mT_e)\} = \mathbf{Q}\delta(n - m). \quad (7)$$

Let us define the following causal filters

$$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}(f) = \mathbf{I} - \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{A}_k e^{-j2\pi f k T_e} \quad (8)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{B}}(f) = \sum_{k=0}^{L+K-1} \mathbf{b}_k e^{-j2\pi f k T_e} = \tilde{\mathbf{D}}(f) \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(f). \quad (9)$$

In [2], the parameters of filters (8) and (9) are estimated with a maximum likelihood estimator. Using the relationship

$$\tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{nn}(f) = \tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{-1}(f) \mathbf{Q} \tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{-*}(f), \quad (10)$$

we deduce from (9) and (10) the expression of the optimum filters (1) and (2). The resulting lengths for $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{MLSE}(f)$ and $\tilde{j}_{MLSE}(f)$ are respectively $Lw = 2K + L$ and $Lj = 2(K + L) - 1$. The computational cost for this method primarily resides in observations and data

correlation matrix. With N pilot symbols, it is approximately worth [5]

$$cost_1 = \frac{T_c}{T_e} \lambda N (KP + P + K + L)^2 \text{ flops}. \quad (11)$$

The second method is simply based on a mean squared error minimization [1], a block diagram is given in figure 1. This method does not rely on channel and interferers power spectrum density estimation, but straightforwardly estimates $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{MLSE}(f)$ and $\tilde{j}_{MLSE}(f)$ filters. It consists of two stages, each one containing a mean squared estimation. The cost generated by this method is [5]

$$cost_2 = \frac{T_c}{T_e} \lambda N (2 + (PLw + Lj)^2) \text{ flops}. \quad (12)$$

Figure 1: Second method structure

3 PERFORMANCES EVALUATION

To evaluate the performances of a receiver, the detection error probability must be computed with a large unknown symbols sequence, and then averaged with respect to all users' scrambling codes and channels realizations. As these averages induce important computational costs, we provide a simplified issue which is valid when the inter-symbol interference is much less powerful than the jammers' signals. If we neglect the inter-symbol interference, all occurs as if *only one binary symbol* were transmitted, and spread by a code sequence $(c_1(0), \dots, c_1(\lambda - 1))$. When there are many jammers, Gaussian property can be assumed, so that the error probability function of the demodulation is obtained from a simple binary hypothesis test

$$Pe = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc}(\sqrt{\frac{S}{B}}) \quad (13)$$

where $\text{erfc}(\cdot)$ denotes the complementary error function, and general expression for S/B is given by

$$\frac{S}{B} = T_e \frac{\left(\Re \int_{-\frac{1}{2T_e}}^{\frac{1}{2T_e}} |\tilde{c}_1(f)|^2 \tilde{\mathbf{w}}(f) \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(f) df \right)^2}{\int_{-\frac{1}{2T_e}}^{\frac{1}{2T_e}} |\tilde{c}_1(f)|^2 \tilde{\mathbf{w}}(f) \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{bb}(f) \tilde{\mathbf{w}}^*(f) df}. \quad (14)$$

If the scrambling code of the mobile of interest is uncorrelated, and if the spreading factor is large, then each term of the ratio can be approximated by its mean, when considering the user's code variations, since their variances tend towards zero. Thus

$$\frac{S}{B} \approx \frac{E\{S\}}{E\{B\}} = \frac{\lambda |v(0)|^2}{\zeta^2}, \quad (15)$$

where ζ^2 is the variance of the noise filtered by $\mathbf{w}(t)$, and $v(t) = \mathbf{w}(t) * \mathbf{g}(t)$. Then the error probability is only conditioned on the channels realizations. The receivers have been studied on the basis of the $E\{S\}/E\{B\}$ ratio obtained for given channels, so as to establish a quick survey of the lengths of the filters in the second method [6], and the number of pilot symbols in both methods [3]. We showed that good performances were obtained with the first method, as long as the length of $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(f)$ was greater than the length of the channel. Filter $\tilde{i}(f)$ is an equalizer: it does not play an important role when the inter-symbol interferences are weak compared to the jammers' power, nevertheless its theoretical ideal length is $Li = \frac{T}{T_e} Lj$, where $Lj = L + Lw - 1$. Assuming perfect power control, both methods provide excellent results with 1536 pilot chips per slot, as allowed by the UMTS [3]. In the following, we are concerned with the near-far effects.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS

In the simulations, the users are uniformly distributed in the cell, and transmit at different speeds. For instance in UMTS, the chip rate is constant, but the data rate differs. Therefore the rate is characterized by the spreading factor. Some of the users, including the user of interest, have low transmitting power, with spreading factor $\lambda = 64$, while others are 16 times more powerful, with spreading factor $\lambda = 4$. The thermal noise is white Gaussian with variance $\sigma^2 = 0.1$. The multipath channels are modeled by the urban COST-207 norm [7], and the antenna is linear with $P = 3$ half wavelength-spaced sensors. The path delays and powers of the Rayleigh channels are recalled in the following table:

delays (μs)	0.0	0.2	0.5	1.6	2.3	5.0
power (dB)	-3	0	-2	-6	-8	-10

The antenna outputs are sampled at rate $T_e = T_c = 1\mu s$. Then each channel that links a mobile to a sensor of the antenna contains $L = 6$ samples. The low-powered

mobile of interest is surrounded by many jammers, including some powerful ones. The inter-symbol interference power is very small compared to the interference resulting from the jammers: consequently the approximation to the error probability involving the simplified ratio (13) is a suitable measure of performance. In this application, filter $\tilde{i}(f)$ has negligible effects on the performances, since its purpose is to combat inter-symbol interference. This motivates us to choose length $Li = 1$ for the simulations. Then the demodulation criterion (4) consists of a correlator, which all the more simplifies the performance evaluation. However, if the user of interest transmitted at high data rate, increasing the length of the filter $\tilde{i}(f)$ would improve the performances.

4.1 Filters lengths influence

In order to choose the most suitable lengths of the receiving filters, the error probability is averaged over a large number of channels, and plotted as a function of parameters Lw and K , assuming that the number of pilot symbols is infinite. Figure 2 illustrates the case of 2 powerful jammers and 30 standard (of low power) jammers. Curves show that the second method is stabilized for $Lw \geq 8$. With this length, filter $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(f)$ is able to collect the power distributed over all the paths, and at the same time it has enough degrees of freedom to correctly reject important part of the jammers. As far as the first method is concerned, the AR order K must be superior to 2 to properly model the colored noise. Thus the $Lw = L$ case, which corresponds to $K = 0$, does not reject the jammers as efficiently as the second method. Nevertheless, it is worthwhile to emphasize that from the computational costs point of view, the first method is slightly favored at the expense of the second one. Indeed, if $Lw = 10$ (i.e. $K = 2$) is chosen for the first method, then $Lw = 6$ must be selected for the second method, so that the costs are of same order of magnitude, whatever the number of pilot symbols. Then the theoretical error probabilities of the first and second method are respectively $P_{th1} = 0.0033$ and $P_{th2} = 0.0037$. As in real life the number of pilot symbols is finite, we compare those asymptotic results to realistic performances computed with 1536 pilot chips (i.e. 24 pilot symbols, if $\lambda = 64$), as fixed by the UMTS norm: $P_1 = 0.0078$ and $P_2 = 0.0074$. This time, the second method is a little more degraded than the first one. Indeed, the number of unknown coefficients to be estimated is higher in the first method (42 coefficients) than in the second one (19 coefficients), which reduces the convergence speed. However, those remarks do not really affect the fact that both methods globally provide similar performances.

4.2 Near-far effects

In this paragraph, the cell capacity is considered, as well as the flexibility in supporting different rates, hence different transmitting powers. If no power control is used,

Figure 2: Error probability

a powerful jammer has obviously much more impact on the performances than a low-powered one. We therefore express the performances according to the number of *virtual* users: each high data rate jammer is assimilated to 16 standard virtual users, since it is 16 times more powerful than the others. Figure 3 represents the performances as the number of virtual users grows, curves corresponding to 0, 2, and 4 powerful jammers. The first and second methods use respectively an AR order $K = 2$, and a length $Lw = 6$. We see that no major difference in performance between the two types of receivers is observed. The RAKE is computed assuming that the user of interest's channel is perfectly estimated, thanks to a very long sequence of pilot symbols. The costs required to estimate the channel are comparable to the spatio-temporal methods of filters estimations. Curves show that for a given jammers' total power, the performances provided by the RAKE are constant, whatever the number of powerful jammers. At the opposite, a substantial gain is observed with the two other receivers, when 4 powerful jammers take the place of 64 standard ones. Remarkably, those receivers can provide a gain of $2.5dB$ in comparison to the RAKE. Therefore the receivers that account for the color of the noise are more near-far resistant than the RAKE receiver. The RAKE attempts to separate the user of interest's message arriving in different paths, and acts as if the jammers' signals were white. For this reason, this receiver is not sensitive to the origin of the interfering power. At the opposite, the treatments proposed in section 2 make the difference between a localized source (one powerful jammer) and a dispersive one (16 standard jammers). Spatial rejection is made easier when the source is well localized.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The multi-sensors receivers at the base station that were developed and analyzed in this paper take into account the spatial and temporal color of the interferers. Two filter estimation methods have been established and analyzed. Simulations reveal that they are well suited to

Figure 3: Error probability - N_p = number of powerful jammers

CDMA multi-rate applications, involving near-far phenomena. In comparison to RAKE that only exploits multipath diversity, the jammers rejection techniques provide significant gain: the most powerful jammers are localized and rejected, so the system can support more users for a given average error probability constraint. Such an improvement must not be neglected. In addition, a simplified expression of error probability provides a convenient way of choosing the most suitable parameters, so as to implement the receiver.

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